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ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE AND MULTIDRUG-RESISTANT INFECTIONS IN PEDIATRIC SURGERY: TREATMENT OF MDR INFECTIONS IN A PATIENT AFTER CORRECTIVE SCOLIOSIS SURGERY

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Antibiotic resistance represents a major challenge in modern medicine, especially in hospital settings, where infections caused by multidrug-resistant microorganisms are increasingly common. The treatment of these infections is often complex, with a limited number of effective antibiotics, prolonged hospitalizations, and high clinical risks, particularly in pediatric patients with comorbidities. A 10-year-old girl with spinal muscular atrophy and neuromuscular scoliosis was hospitalized for corrective scoliosis surgery. The intervention was uneventful; however, on the tenth postoperative day, she developed fever, wound dehiscence, and purulent discharge from the surgical wound. Empirical antibiotic therapy (cefazolin, amikacin) and fluconazole were initiated. During the postoperative course, *Enterococcus faecium*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Candida* spp. were isolated, and the therapy was changed (tigecycline, clindamycin). After two weeks, her condition worsened, with the development of pneumonia, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Enterobacter hormaechei*, and *Enterococcus faecalis* were isolated from the wound. Therapy was adjusted accordingly. During her further hospitalization, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, resistant to most antibiotics but sensitive to colistin and intermediately resistant to imipenem-cilastatin, was isolated from the wound. Anaerobic bacteria (*Bacteroides fragilis*, *Streptococcus parasanguinis*) sensitive to clindamycin were also detected. During the hospitalization, the girl experienced two urinary tract infections, the first caused by *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, treated with imipenem-cilastatin, and the second caused by *Klebsiella aerogenes*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Citrobacter koseri*, which showed sensitivity to ciprofloxacin. The wound was regularly dressed under general anesthesia with the application of a VAC system. After four months, the patient was discharged in stable condition. This case highlights the challenges in treating MDR infections in pediatric patients with comorbidities. Microbiological diagnostics and personalized therapy are crucial for effective management. The rise of resistant microorganisms, particularly in pediatric surgery, emphasizes the need for early identification and targeted therapy. Prolonged hospital stays increase the risk of such infections, making a tailored, multidimensional approach essential. The treatment of MDR infections requires timely diagnostics, a multidisciplinary approach, and rational use of antibiotics. This case highlights the importance of an individualized treatment approach in pediatric surgery.

Keywords: antibiotic resistance, MDR, pediatric surgery, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, microbiological diagnostic